

FACTORS FOR IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF TEACHERS IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF LABOR PROTECTION TO "RAILWAY COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article talks about the teacher's pedagogical skills in teaching the subject of "Labor protection".

Key words: Pedagogical science, specialist, art teaching, training personnel.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматривается, что обучение предмета "Охрана труда" во многом зависит от работы преподавателя и его профессионального опыта.

Калит сўзлар: Педагогик билим, етук мутахассис, дарс бериш санъати, кадрлар тайёрлаш.

Globally, science and technology have become the main foundation of global development. Both entities serve to improve the quality of life as these new discoveries emerge from science and technology. Although the subject of "Labor protection" plays an important role in the world of science, technology and natural sciences, it always faces difficulties in mastering by students and teachers of general and vocational education. Great efforts have been made to strengthen the material and technical base for mastering the science of "Labor protection" by students of general education and vocational education, and to further strengthen educational and scientific laboratories in the priority directions of higher education by equipping them with modern equipment. creates the need to develop the technology of performing chemical experiments on the basis of virtual laboratories and to improve the teaching methodology. Today, political, social and economic changes are taking place in the life of our republic. These changes also affect the natural process of professional education, which is carried out in accordance with the society's demand for highly qualified, solid and well-educated, capable personnel who work on it. Currently, the application of advanced pedagogical technologies in the teaching process of the new growing generation is rapidly developing. It also affects the natural process of professional education, which is conducted in accordance with the demand for skilled personnel working on it. Currently, the application of advanced pedagogical technologies in the teaching process of the new growing generation is rapidly developing. It also affects the natural process of professional education, which is conducted in accordance with the demand for skilled personnel working on it. Currently, the application of advanced pedagogical technologies in the teaching process of the new growing generation is rapidly developing.

Raising the generation that will be the future of independent Uzbekistan is a delicate process that requires a lot of attention. Therefore, the teacher, pupil and student should carefully

monitor the formation process. A teacher should have pedagogical knowledge and skills while managing the pedagogical process. Only then the teacher can master the essence and dialectics of pedagogical phenomena, the method of pedagogical work, professional technology, and professional pedagogical skills.

A teacher who has pedagogical knowledge and skills must first know the methodological foundations of pedagogy, the laws and factors of personal development, the essence, goals, and tasks of the national personnel training program. Most of the pedagogues working in the educational system are deeply aware of the necessity and importance of pedagogical skills in the process of education and training [1].

Currently, the successful implementation of the national personnel training program in our country depends to a large extent on the teacher's activity and increasing his professional prestige. Therefore, raising a healthy, well-rounded generation depends on the level, preparation and dedication of the pedagogue working in the continuous education system, and his attitude to the work of teaching and educating the young generation. The teacher fulfills the social task of the society, therefore, the teacher must meet certain social-political, pedagogical and personal requirements in the preparation of all-round mature specialists.

Therefore, a teacher should have a belief in the idea of independence, comprehensively developed scientific thinking, professional knowledge, that is, a deep knowledge of his subject, a master of pedagogical communication, pedagogical-psychological and methodological knowledge and skills, as well as the ability to quickly solve various pedagogical tasks, study situations, and evaluate should get It is necessary to have the ability to choose the most appropriate methods and means of pedagogical influence.

One of the main tasks defined in the "National Personnel Training Program" is the development of the integration of science, education and production. In order to solve this problem, there must be interdependence, compatibility and complementarity between information, pedagogical and production technologies.

Nowadays, it is required that every pedagogue or production worker should be familiar with the set of information communication technologies and technical systems. At the same time, the pedagogue is an active participant in the production, the production specialist should also perform the role of a pedagogue [2].

For this reason, they strive to continuously improve their skills, acquire modern knowledge and experience in accordance with the high demands of today, and work creatively. However,

we must also admit that some teachers in educational institutions do not feel the importance of improving their pedagogical skills, are not interested in studying the requirements of the Law on Education, the national training program, and look superficially at the scientificity of the educational process, its relevance to the requirements of the times, and its connection with life and practice. , they do not always remember the scientific and ideological educational unity of the taught subjects. This is the reason for the insufficient level and level of knowledge of the student and students, and they fall behind in mastering the educational programs.

In the process of implementing the continuous education system, when it comes to teaching and educating the young generation, this extremely complex and multifaceted task can be performed only by teaching staff with qualified pedagogical skills.

Therefore, teaching is a great art. One or another pedagogue cannot easily achieve this art by himself. For this, only patriotic, hard-working people can achieve the teaching profession, i.e., the desire to become a real trainer of a healthy generation, who quickly and deeply understands the demands of the times, who consistently realizes his scientific, socio-political level, and pedagogical skills.

Pedagogical skill is not an innate talent or a trait that is passed from generation to generation, it requires work, research, and creative work to achieve it. Therefore, pedagogical skill is not a standard for all teachers, that is, a uniform method of work, but it is formed and developed in the process of each teacher's work on himself, creative work [1].

In this process, it is necessary for another teacher to learn the pedagogical skills and experiences of an advanced teacher, to use them creatively, to enrich his work with advanced experiences.

The teacher's pedagogic skill is evident mainly in classroom and auditorium activities. Because training is the main work of the teacher in the school according to its content and essence. Therefore, it should be scientific, ideological and popular, and be related to the level of preparation of students. In the educational process, there is a need for lively language, exchange of ideas, sincere attitude, respect, and cooperation in achieving the main goal between the teacher and the students. Classes, lectures and other educational activities, whose content is shallow, separated from practical experience and life, consisting of general words and dry exhortations, conducted superficially for the sake of formality, do not interest

students, do not feed them scientifically and ideologically. Therefore, training sessions should be organized in such a way that

The higher effectiveness of the educational process depends on the teacher's scientific potential, reputation in front of young people, personal qualities, scientific talent, experience and skills in the field of education, and friendly relations with students.

The effectiveness of pedagogical activity also depends on the teacher's pedagogical ability. Ability appears and develops in the process of activity. For example, the ability to know, the ability to explain, the ability to speak, the ability to gain reputation, the ability to deal with others.

Pedagogical abilities and skills are not easily formed in a teacher. In order to achieve his goal, a person who has chosen this profession must continuously study, search, work creatively, quickly understand the reality of our independent country and deeply feel how necessary his work is for the country [2].

While thinking about the teacher's pedagogical skills, we should pay attention to his consciousness, loyalty to the national idea and ideology, wide range of knowledge and thought, and his attitude to his task. Especially in pedagogical skills, it is necessary to take into account the need for a wide range of ideas of the teacher. Because if a person's knowledge and thinking are not perfect, he cannot reach maturity. In fact, a person solves this or that issue, of course, through thought. Therefore, a person who aspires to become a pedagogical master must always expand his knowledge, update the ideas and thoughts that have a spiritual and moral impact on the student. For this, he should read and study a lot. When evaluating the teacher's pedagogical skills, the extent to which he can organize education is important [1].

Perfect organization of lessons and lectures in continuing education is the primary task of the teacher. The subjects taught at a high level are kept in the minds of young people for a long time and influence the formation of their faith, beliefs and ideologies. For this reason, the teacher's scientific level, his attitude to his duties, his enthusiasm for coaching young people, and his pedagogical skills are visible in the lessons and lectures. The quality of the lesson and lecture also determines the level of evaluation of the activity of the science teacher.

In interactive learning, lecture and practice are considered as parts of a single lesson, and this is determined by the interaction between the teacher and the student and the level of active participation of the students during the lesson. It is known that if teacher activity is provided in traditional lecture classes, student activity is required in practical training. In the interactive style, the teacher is required to skillfully move from one view of the level of interaction between the student and the teacher to another depending on the topic during the lesson. The process of interactive lecture classes can be roughly divided as follows, depending on the purpose and task of the subject and the needs of learners [2].

In conclusion, today, first of all, our young people should be satisfied with the lessons of their coaches. May their scientific dreams be awakened, their thinking should be developed, their practical activity, creative ability, passion for study and work should increase. Let them feel that they have gained knowledge and skills, and that they have received spiritual nourishment, not with the grades they received after the training session. Meaningful, interesting and understandable education firmly connects the heart and soul of the teacher and the students, strengthens sincere respect and mutual trust between them. For this, first of all, the teacher must master his subject and the methods of teaching it perfectly, the high level of culture characteristic of a teacher-coach, respect and love for his students, interest in their lives and knowledge of their mental states, understanding, calmness,

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